

Apple - ResearchKit

Description

Apple introduced its open source ResearchKit platform in the spring of 2015 and it has been used to develop apps that are used in the collection of health data with the expressed purpose of making it easier to enrol participants in clinical trials and research studies. Many of the projects built on the ResearchKit platform are collaborative initiatives between researchers in the medical and academic communities, software and IT companies and various public and private funding bodies.

ResearchKit apps already developed include Autism and Beyond, a collaboration between Duke University and the University of Cape Town, which uses facial recognition algorithms to screen children as young as 18 months for autism, leading to earlier diagnosis, intervention and improved patient health outcomes. ResearchKit is being used by researchers in the United States, the United Kingdom and Australia to recruit between 50,000 and 100,000 women who have experienced postpartum depression for a large scale clinical research project designed to identify possible genetic markers for this illness. Women download the app, complete a screening questionnaire and then may be selected to provide a DNA sample through a spit collection kit that is mailed to each participant. The project is a multi-year undertaking and includes sharing of research data on a scale that is unprecedented.

Economic benefits

ResearchKit is available to developers free of charge as an open source data platform. Economic benefits include reduced costs for participant recruitment and retention in clinical studies and future application of data and research

findings to commercialisation. These could include new treatment procedures, the development of new or improved drug treatments and changes to current treatment procedures that could save significant costs to health care systems and providers. Additionally, ResearchKit works directly with Apple's HealthKit and recently launched CareKit to simultaneously collect valuable data for research while improving the user experience in understanding personalised health data.

Health/social benefits

Difficulties in the recruitment of participants for clinical research is often one of the largest barriers to conducting large scale randomised controlled trials or population level health research. ResearchKit leverages the popularity of Apple's iPhone and widespread global ownership while giving researchers the technological tools to develop apps that can be used for participant recruitment and ongoing engagement. Recruitment of more research participants increases the opportunity to identify disease cause and progression and development of new treatment options that improve individual health outcomes.

Supporting links

<http://www.apple.com/researchkit/>

Accessed 02 April 2016.

'Who we are' <http://www.pactfortheure.com/who-we-are/>

Accessed 03 April 2016.

http://bit.ly/Postpartum_Progress

Accessed 04 May 2016.